

EXAMINING THE IMAGE OF WOMEN IN SELECTED FLAVOUR AND TIMAYA'S MUSICAL VIDEOS AMONG UNDERGRADUATES OF UNICAL, CROSS RIVER STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study examined the image of women in selected Flavour and Timaya's musical videos among the undergraduates of the University of Calabar (UNICAL), Cross River State Nigeria. Using the survey method, the study sampled the views of 381 respondents out of a population of 29,645 from UNICAL. The broad objective of the study was to discover the picture painted of women in Flavour's 'Ukwu Sara Mbara' and Timaya's 'Bum Bum'. With the result of χ^2 calculated ($300.65 > 9.488$), it was empirically supported that the dominant marketing appeal adopted in Flavour's 'Ukwu Sara Mbara' and Timaya's 'Bum Bum' was likely a factor that won the patronage of undergraduates. The study concluded that the woman is over-represented in the media but only as a marketing strategy; again, Flavour's 'Ukwu Sara Mbara' and Timaya's 'Bum Bum' are awash with hyper-sexualized images of the female gender; a pattern that is culturally anti-African but highly embraced by the younger generation. Among

the recommendations is that the entertainment and media industries should ensure the promotion of local content through musical videos as well as reduce the flooding of the local media with foreign contents that promote cultural imperialism. The objectification of women and their use as marketing strategies should be checkmated by the media.

Keywords: Image, Women, Musical Videos, Undergraduates, Ukwu Sara Mbara, Bum Bum,

Introduction

The portrayal of the women folk in the entertainment industry within the last two decades has become increasingly worrisome (Mbah, 2022). Generally, the media are utilized for the dissemination of information, ideas, culture, attitude, and feelings, among others (Okunna & Omenugha, 2012). In a bid to carry out the above function, the manner of presentations and interpretation of media content influences audience' perception. Basically, the media is a great purveyor of culture, hence, Okunna (1998, p. 141) wrote that “. . .mass communication is a major carrier of culture, and that the mass media are cultural instruments which supply the cultural fare and shape the cultural experience of many millions of people in the modern world”. Other researchers (Ekwunife, Chukwu, Agha, Ukeje & Anih, 2021, p. 6) lent support to this when they argued that “the entire world has been miniaturized into a global village where the new media technology helps to transmit cultures globally - particularly the cultures of the developed world due to media dependency. Hence, the relationship between the media and culture dissemination is very strong. An aspect of these cultures brings to limelight how the female gender is perceived in both the developed and developing nations. Scholarly debates in the field of mass communication (Ndolo, 2011; Serena, Mariska & Sadza, 2017) identified some areas where the image of the woman in the study calls for attention. Some of the arguments bother on female under-representation in the media, gender imbalance in top media positions with the female taking the lower cadre, women being reported on the shoulder of men, women as objects of marketing evidenced by the nudity in advertising and the entertainment industry, particularly in musical videos.

In the music industry all over the world, hypersexualized portrayal and other negative presentations of the women are prevalent (Idorenyin, 2019; Glantz, 2013), particularly in Nigeria where pop music is thriving at a geometric progression. Sometimes, these images of the women folk in the media are culture-determined, hence, the woman is stereotyped as a marketing strategy. An examination of modern hip-hop music in Nigeria reveals those musical artistes target women characters with special attention to them using their bodies for the economic gains of the musicians.

Ekwenchi and Duru (2016) lent credence to the popularity of Nigerian music videos and their sexualized nature in the country, especially among the youths, whether students or not. This implies that the youths are responsive to the sexualized musical videos since such musical videos appear to aptly present and represent their era with the show of women in skimpy clothes, nude appearances and erotic dance steps. Earlier studies (Jimoh, 2014; Ajose, 2015) also agreed that such sexualized musical videos evoke some feelings in the minds of the young persons as much as many of the youths find such sexualized exposures “undignifying, debasing and not representative of the role of women in the Nigerian society” (Ekwenchi & Dunu, 2016, p.1).

Frisby and Aubrey (2012, p. 66) noted that “Music videos have been critiqued as having misogynistic messages and images... dominant discourse in music videos reproduce distorted ideologies of women's sexuality”. Other researches (Hooks, 1992; Morgan, 1999) argued that this hypersexualized representation of the female gender in the media is more visible among women of black race but this can as well be contested, particularly in the contemporary times when the mass media, especially the new media show that sexualized musical videos of women is a global trend (Idorenyin, 2019; Frisby & Aubrey, 2012); they also contended that even female music artistes have become visible brand by also being the ones that objectify their bodies mainly for economic reasons. Majority of the musical videos are

owned by men but feature sexualized bodies of women to catch attention and gain patronage. Examples in our immediate environment can be seen in the music of Flavour, Burna Boy, Timaya, Davido, Wizkid, Olamide, Naira Marley, among others. In the Nigerian society, musicals such as *Na abania (This Night)*, *Ukwusarambara (Spacious Buttocks)*, and others have attracted many mordant criticisms for their sexualization of the female gender in as much as they are very popular and command sweeping embrace among the younger generation.

The prevalence of sexualized portrayal of the female gender in Nigeria musical video has highly been attributed to the infiltration of foreign culture through modern media technologies to the detriment of indigenous norms and cultures. Simon and Besong (2016) bemoaned this fate when they hinted that lack of censorship of media content, particularly the broadcast media has a damning effect on local culture, hence, cultural erosion. Mbah (2022) posited that the world was evolving and technology gaining ground, which permitted western cultures take over the industry thereby making obscene dressing and nudity to be perceived rather as a cultural display of the body art.

Writing on the implication of the hypersexualized presentation of the female gender in musical videos, Ajose (2015) observed that in the present time, caution is no longer applied in the entertainment world, hence, a display of boobs, naked laps and other subtle sexually provocative parts of the body. Such presentation is more acceptable by the younger ones who are still in their sexually active stage, quite exuberant and impressionistic.

On these premises, this study examined the image of women in the selected Flavour and Timaya's musical videos. From observation, Flavour appears to have hinged his videos on hypersexualized presentation of the female body. Examples of such musical videos are: *Ukwu Nwanyi Owerri (Owerri Woman's Buttocks)* which lyrics strongly depict the woman as sex object: 'My Sweetie' which shows uncovered breasts of a lady; 'Looking Nyash' (*Looking Buttocks*) which features almost fat naked ladies shaking their buttocks; *Nneketa (As I Keep Looking)* which centres purely on the woman with strong sex appeal. Other musicals by Flavour in this category are 'Ukwu Sara Mbara' (*Spacious Buttocks*) which the singer describes as the delight of a man; *Nabania (This Night)* where the lyrics complement the female nude videos by explaining that "everything will happen this night" between the buttocks and men, among others.

Timaya in the same vein has released several musical videos which include: 'Cold Outside Feat' that features a lady in a romantic relationship with a man; 'Dem Mama' which features the impoverishment and sufferings of Nigerians; 'I can't kill myself', 'Bum Bum' which show nude ladies in a very offensive buttocks-shaking and amorous expression, 'Balance', 'Sanko', 'Shake yuh Bum Bum', 'Bang Bang', *Fall in*, among others

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

- (i) What is the awareness level of Flavour's 'Ukwu Sara Mbara' and Timaya's 'Bum Bum' among undergraduates at the University of Calabar, Cross River State?
- (ii) What is the dominant marketing appeal adopted in Flavour's 'Ukwu Sara Mbara' and Timaya's 'Bum Bum' that won patronage among undergraduates of the University of Calabar in Cross River State?

Hypothesis

H0: The dominant marketing appeal adopted in Flavour's 'Ukwu Sara Mbara' and Timaya's 'Bum Bum' is not likely a factor that won the patronage of undergraduates of the University of Calabar in Cross River State.

Review of Literature

Female Representation in Musical videos

Female representation in musical videos refers to how females are portrayed in music videos. This explains the overall image or impression which viewers of such musicals have as a result of exposures. In the entertainment industry, music- whether audio or video is one aspect of entertainment that gains wide acceptance. It is a prominent and pervasive type of entertainment.

While musical videos form a nucleus in the entertainment industry with sweeping attention particularly by the younger generation, there is obviously a very high frequency of hyper-sexualized female sexual objectification of women in them (Qamar, Pasha & Ali, 2021). It is believed that the sexual objectification of women in musical videos is a prevailing phenomenon, one that has driven the American Psychological Association to investigate the degree of sexual objectification of women in musical videos. Aside musicals, there is evidence of high portrayal of sexualized bodies of women in the general entertainment content in the media (Ali, 2018). In the view of Mbah (2022), the rate of female nudity in musical videos is alarming and this is traceable to the fact that men who in most cases own the musicals, do not care so much about the moral effect of such nude exposures, because of the desire to sell the video. Mba (2022, p.1) lamented that "the image of the music industry at large especially in our country Nigeria was envisaged as entertainment norms, but in recent times, they have more nudity to showcase than talent and content".

Researches (Ajose, 2015; Qamar *et al*, 2021) are of the opinion that the high rate of sexualized presentation of the female gender in music content, especially motion pictures and consumer culture accord women unrealistic representations. Musical videos that present women's naked bodies are seen to ironically motivate the feminine gender to develop sexiness, submissive attitude, powerlessness and the character of passivity as criteria for being women. This explains that often times, there is the feeling or perception of what a woman should be, hence, the weakness and fragility which the women show. Jordan (2019) argued that the society is very receptive of nude and sexualized images of women in musicals. As much as this may seem untrue, the media portrayal of such half-naked contents suggests societal admiration and acceptance of such. Often, the media shows the women in terms of physical attractiveness and aesthetics by presenting them as objects and prizes that can be won, especially by men. In the media, the portrayal of the woman as living for the sexual pleasure of men is therefore common (Qamar *et al*, 2021).

Women are at the centre as each of these musicals which targets them as characters and marketing strategy. It could be well said that women have become objects of inspiration for hip pop artistes in Nigeria as everything about women: butts, boobs, waist, and breasts form parts of these songs. In socio-cultural events and at the individual level, it is common to see young boys and girls recite and dance to these videos, a phenomenon that shows the high degree of spread and acceptance of these musical videos. These women characters also form heavy weight of the financial returns made by these male artistes. Idorenyin (2019) argued that the prevalence of hyper sexualized females in Nigerian musical videos is a global trend, pointing out that the motives are still vague.

For the generation of 1980s and 1990s, a sharp distinction can easily be seen between the musical videos of the past and the present. It was in preservation of cultural values and norms that the songs of Onyeka

Onwenu and Christie Essien Igbokwe presented women characters with well knitted hairstyle and wholesome costuming. In the hit song of Christie Essien Igbokwe 'Seun Rere', a gentle appearance of characters was seen. In the hit track, 'Happy Birthday' by Evi-Edna Ogholi, and other performances by artistes who could be considered pop-stars in the past decades, they did not deviate from cultural values of the society. If a comparative study was to be made between the old and the new, there would be witnessed a sharp departure from the decent to the indecent, particularly in the aspect of costuming female characters in these musical videos. Today, the female artistes/characters are costumed sexily, straining the maternal images that prevailed in the past decades. A viewing of present performance like Flavour, Timaya, Waje, Tiwa Savage, Omawunmi, may seem to suggest that musical videos that are similar to those of the 1980s and 1990s would neither sell nor conform to the present.

Ajose (2015) explained that in the Nigeria landscape, musical videos have gone beyond moral functions to the display of gangsterism, sex and violence. The view is that Nigerian cultural musical videos strain standard, showing a connect between hyper sexualized musical videos and violent social behaviours such as rape, sexual harassment, etc. According to Ekwenchi and Duru (2016), the image of women in Nigeria musical videos is sexualized and forms a subject of study. Their research showed that female characters in video games were objectified and sexualized by their costume.

Ekwenchi and Duru (2016) found strong connect between misogynist and the consumption of musical videos that debase women. The idea is in two ways; while musical videos that present women derogatorily have the capacity to cause the society to see women as mere objects; the creation of such humiliating views of female sexuality could be a product of misogynist thinking and orientation, in any case, some women are still opposed to these portrayals of the female folk in the media. These could be explained from the angle of the cognitive make up of oneself which serves as intervening variables determining one's perception of self, despite media content and exposure. Music is a universal phenomenon showing language, space, time and culture. Sarna (2021) noted that hip hop music has overtaken rock and is the most widely consumed genre of music all over the globe. This universality has an impact on the popularity, hence, massive impact on the audience. Writing on this impact, Sarna (2021) observed that among 403 rap song studied, 37% showed women as mere objects of male desire and pleasure. Such musical production shows women driven about in flashy and posh cars as if that is all they live for. Whatever men do with them to be driven about in those expensive cars is what they live for-sexual objectification. These image and impressions also register in the minds of the young girls and form their perceptions of the folk, hence, distorted reality.

Today's hip-hop music has been accused of having no moral message to pass across to the younger generation. The pictures below are shots of musical videos showing male and female characters in compromising positions. The ladies in the musical videos swing their waists amorously from the start to the end. The same story goes to the video '*Shake your bum bum*' by Timaya which features white vixens shaking their buttocks with vehemence with the video having no clear story line. A shocking aspect of this Timaya's musical video is the brazen manner in which the female characters shake their buttocks, and this made the video to be described as 'Not suitable for work'-NSFW (Ajose, 2015). See pictures below:

Timaya's musical videos showing the hypersexualized woman
Source: Mbah (2022)

Flavour's musical

Source: Ajose (2015)

Empirical Review

Qamar *et al.* (2021) examined female objectification in music videos from Martha Nussbaum's perspective. The study was hinged on the objectification theory while the design adopted was the survey. The study showed a strong significant relationship between music videos and sexualized portrayal of women. The study further revealed that there is a higher frequency of sexual objectification in some particular music videos. It also showed that musical videos featured male models who abuse women sexually. Women were found to be represented as semi-nude, silent, and submissive in front of male artistes.

Oberiri (2019), using the qualitative approach, studied the portrayal and objectification of Women in Music Videos. The finding of the study revealed that female characters are more sexually objectified and held to stricter appearance standards as well as demonstrating sexually alluring behaviour. Sexual objectification was also found to be more common in the R&B hip hop and pop videos than country videos. The study concluded that African-American rappers represent African – American women in more sexist manner than their white counterparts in the name of hip-hop.

The perception of undergraduates on the image of women in Nigerian music videos was studied by Ekwenchi and Duru (2016). The study used the survey method and found out that musical videos featured women in skimpy wears with erotic dance steps which evoke in the minds of the undergraduates a highly sexualized image of the female gender. It also revealed that though there is a significant difference in the way male and female undergraduates interpret the nature and impact of women representation, those videos are unlikely to influence the self-image of the female respondents who presently see women's image as undignifying.

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on the objectification theory propounded by Frederickson and Robert in 1997 (Qamar *et al.*, 2021). This theory explains that sexual objectification of the bodies of the female gender teaches women to internalize an outsider's perspective on the self, so that these females perceive themselves as objects to be assessed by others. In essence, this is seen as self-objectification. By objectification theory, it holds that the female gender is nothing but an object which has no capacity to control self but relies on external forces to form opinion about its worth, usefulness and self-definition.

It is considered most relevant for this study considering how the musical videos portray the female characters as objects who exist to satisfy the sexual desire of men. These sexualized musical videos demean and undignify the woman and forms the basis for the woman's self-assessment.

Summary

This section re-examined existing literatures that studied the image of women in musical videos. The reviews showed that generally, the image of women in most media content is demeaning, and that the woman is under-represented in the media except as marketing strategies where the female gender achieves over-representation. The image of the woman in musical videos has become a world-wide phenomenon as musical videos feature hyper-sexualized women bodies which make women believe that they live as objects whose worth lies in their beauty and physical appearance to attract men to themselves. The role of women in musical videos has thus been stereotyped and even women have resorted to self-objectification as a norm. This entire idea is also seen as the product of a patriarchal system.

Methodology

The study adopted the descriptive survey design which gave the researchers sufficient information about what obtains in the entire population. The population of the study is 29,645 consisting of all the undergraduate students of the University of Calabar (Edeh, 2022). A sample size of 381 was chosen based on the Singh and Masuki (2014) online sample size table which stated that a sample of 381 is appropriate for a population within the range of 30,000-50,000. This sample was chosen considering its proximity with the provision in the sample size determination in Singh and Masuki online sample size table. The simple random sampling technique was used for the study because it enabled the sample to be studied directly, by giving everyone equal chance of being included in the sample. The researchers with the help of five research assistants distributed the questionnaire to the population. The questionnaire was structured in four-point Likert type rating scale of Strongly Agree, Agree, Disagree and Strongly Disagree. Each research question has a corresponding set of five questions derived from the objective that gave rise to it.

The instrument was administered to the respondents by the researchers with the help of the research assistants who were adequately briefed in a training session on what was expected of them during the exercise. Data collected were presented in tables. The respondents' demographic data were analyzed using the simple percentage. While the mean method was used to analyse the general information gathered on the topic of study. The decision rule for accepting that respondents agreed on a questionnaire item was that the calculated mean rating for a questionnaire item was greater than 3.0. The hypothesis was tested using Chi-square statistics.

Data Presentation and Analysis

The researchers administered three hundred and eighty-one (381) copies of the questionnaire by hand and three hundred and sixty-eight (368) were correctly filled and returned, giving a percentage response of 97%. The table below shows the demographic information of respondents.

Table 1. Analysis of Demographic Data of the Sampled Population

Case	Item	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	169	46%
	Female	99	27%
	Total	368	100%

Age	18 – 22	214	58%
	23 – 27	97	26%
	28 – 32	48	13%
	33 – above	09	3%
	Total	368	100%
Level of Study	100	106	28%
	200	113	31%
	300	87	24%
	400	51	14%
	500	11	3%
	Total	368	100%
Religion	Christianity	337	92%
	Islam	12	3%
	Others	19	5%
	Total	368	100%

Table one above indicates that male undergraduate students were more receptive to the instrument than the females who are represented by only 27% of the sampled population. The age range reveals that the younger youths were actively involved in the study, shown by the age ranges of 18 - 22 and 23 – 27. Levels 100 and 200 featured more prominently in the sample while 98% of the sample are Christians. Generally, the demographic data showed that the younger generation that cuts across different characteristics was well represented in the study, hence, a good sample for the topic of study.

Table 2: Mean Responses of Respondents on the Awareness Level of Flavour's 'Ukwu Sara Mbara' and Timaya's 'Bum Bum'

S/ N	ITEM	SA	A	D	SD	FX	X	DECISION
1	I know about Flavour's 'Ukwu Sara Mbara' and Timaya's 'Bum Bum'	321	44	2	1	1421	3.86	Accepted
2	I have viewed the musical videos of Flavour's 'Ukwu Sara Mbara' and Timaya's 'Bum Bum'	188	121	43	16	1217	3.31	Accepted
3	I am a devoted fan of Flavour and Timaya as musical artistes	53	173	98	44	971	2.64	Rejected
4	Flavour's 'Ukwu Sara Mbara' and Timaya's 'Bum Bum' have gained wide popularity among the younger generation	87	271	4	6	1175	3.19	Accepted
5	Flavour's 'Ukwu Sara Mbara' and Timaya's 'Bum Bum' feature prominently in the media	91	210	47	20	1108	3.01	Accepted
	Grand Mean						16.01	

The Table above with a mean value of 3.86 and 3.31 clearly shows that Flavour's 'Ukwu Sara Mbara' and Timaya's 'Bum Bum' are well known by the respondents, and have gained wide popularity among the people. The mean of 2.64 indicates that 142 respondents are not devoted fans of the artistes under study,

showing that in spite of the popularity of the songs, not all the people are fans. The high level of awareness recorded and corroborated by a grand mean of 16.01 is indicative of the role of the media in popularizing entertainment.

Table 3: Mean Responses of Respondents on Dominant Marketing Appeal Adopted in Flavour’s ‘Ukwu Sara Mbara’ and Timaya’s ‘Bum Bum’ to Win Patronage

S/N	ITEM	SA	A	D	SD	FX	X	DECISION
16	I am attracted to Flavour’s ‘Ukwu Sara Mbara’ and Timaya’s ‘Bum Bum’ because of the lyrics	55	287	5	21	1112	3.02	Accepted
17	The dress pattern of players in Flavour’s ‘Ukwu Sara Mbara’ and Timaya’s ‘Bum Bum’ is inviting	76	257	11	24	1121	3.05	Accepted
18	Flavour’s ‘Ukwu Sara Mbara’ and Timaya’s ‘Bum Bum’ would attract less patronage if the dress pattern was otherwise	13	167	168	20	909	2.47	Rejected
19	The younger generation will most likely prefer Flavour’s ‘Ukwu Sara Mbara’ and Timaya’s ‘Bum Bum’ because of the dominant sex appeal	101	221	26	20	1139	3.10	Accepted
20	Flavour’s ‘Ukwu Sara Mbara’ and Timaya’s ‘Bum Bum’ are suitable for sensational occasions	49	241	48	30	1045	2.84	Rejected
Grand Mean							14.48	

From table 3, respondents with the value of 3.02 are attracted to Flavour’s ‘Ukwu Sara Mbara’ and Timaya’s ‘Bum Bum’ by the lyrics. A frequency of 333, that is, the mean of 3.05 shows the role of dress pattern and sexual advances (particularly of females) in appealing to listeners and viewers. The value of 3.10 indicates that the sex appeal used in Flavour’s ‘Ukwu Sara Mbara’ and Timaya’s ‘Bum Bum’ is a strong attraction to exposure by the youths. By implication, all the items in the table above indicate a strong attachment of the respondents to the sexual appeal of the selected videos as marketing strategies.

Test of Hypothesis and Data Analysis

H0: The dominant marketing appeal adopted in Flavour’s ‘Ukwu Sara Mbara’ and Timaya’s ‘Bum Bum’ is not likely a factor to win the patronage of undergraduates of the University of Calabar in Cross River State.

Here, a Chi-square (X^2) was used to test the hypothesis and data analysed. Thus;

$$X^2 = (f_o - f_e)^2 / f_e$$

Table 4: Chi-Square (X^2) Table

Observed (f_o)	Expected (f_e)	$(f_o - f_e)$	$(f_o - f_e)^2$	$(f_o - f_e)/f_e$
342	293.4	48.6	2361.96	8.05
333	293.4	39.6	1568.16	5.34
180	293.4	-113.4	12859.56	43.83
322	293.4	28.6	817.96	2.79
290	293.4	-3.4	11.56	0.04
26	74.6	-48.6	2961.96	36.09
35	74.6	-39.6	1568.16	21.02
188	74.6	113.4	12859.56	172.38
46	74.6	-28.6	817.96	10.96
78	74.6	3.4	11.56	0.15

Since $300.65 > 9.488$ which is the value of alpha (0.05) in the probability level, it is therefore empirically supported and the null hypothesis (H_0) rejected. Hence, the dominant marketing appeal adopted in Flavour's '*Ukwu Sara Mbara*' and Timaya's '*Bum Bum*' is likely a factor to win the patronage of undergraduates of the University of Calabar in Cross River State

Discussion of Findings

The purpose of this study is to examine the image of the woman in selected Flavour and Timaya's musical videos. The four research questions whose responses gave rise to the corresponding hypothesis as formulated and tested showed the following results:

1. What is the awareness level of Flavour's '*Ukwu Sara Mbara*' and Timaya's '*Bum Bum*' among undergraduates at the University of Calabar, Cross River State?

Responses in table 2 showed that the undergraduates at the University of Calabar, Cross River State are well aware of Flavour's '*Ukwu Sara Mbara*' and Timaya's '*Bum Bum*'. From the responses, the awareness level could be said to be very high as corroborated by a mean value of 3.86 and 3.19. This awareness is particularly recorded among the younger generation which signaled a wide acceptance of the musical videos among them. Such awareness is highly promoted by the media through which the sample is heavily exposed to the musical videos. Though the value of 2.64 confirmed that not all the respondents are fans of the artistes under study, there is the indication that the majority of them are. This influence of the media in bringing the musical videos to the limelight is corroborated by Ekwenchi and Durul (2016) when they observed that the media- both the conventional and the social media, are highly instrumental to the popularity of sexualized musical videos. The researchers pointed out clearly that without the media, musical videos lack the power to command the attention they do.

2. What is the dominant marketing appeal adopted in Flavour's '*Ukwu Sara Mbara*' and Timaya's '*Bum Bum*' to win patronage among undergraduates of the University of Calabar in Cross River State?

Looking at the marketing appeal used in Flavour's '*Ukwu Sara Mbara*' and Timaya's '*Bum Bum*' to win patronage, responses showed that the lyrics, otherwise seen as the language of production, is attractive to the audience. In the musical videos, the dress pattern, especially that of ladies, commands overwhelming patronage. This is shown with a mean of 3.05 as the respondents showed that such musical videos would receive less attention if the females in them dressed decently. Data presented indicated that the sex appeal that dominates Flavour's '*Ukwu Sara Mbara*' and Timaya's '*Bum Bum*' is an effective marketing strategy

which is result oriented. This implies that the woman in these musical videos is a means to an end as well as portrays an objectified person. Relating these thoughts to the literature in this work, Jordan (2019) and Qamar *et al* (2021) noted that musical videos that present women's naked bodies are seen to ironically motivate the feminine gender to develop sexiness, submissive attitude, powerlessness and the character of passivity as criteria for being women. This explains that often times, there is the feeling or perception of what a woman should be, hence, the weakness and fragility which the women show. The media portrayal of such half-naked contents suggests societal admiration and acceptance of such. Often, the media show the women in terms of physical attractiveness and aesthetics by presenting them as objects and prizes that can be won, especially by men. In the media, the portrayal of the woman as living for the sexual pleasure of men is therefore common.

The above thought is better explained by the objectification theory; hence, objectification theory holds that the female gender is nothing but an object which has no capacity to control self but relies on external forces to form opinion about its worth, usefulness and self-definition. The focus of objectification theory is on self-objectification which is the outcome of media representation of women such as can be seen in the musical videos of Flavour and Timaya. As a result of being objectified, the female gender perceives herself as objects to be looked at and evaluated, and this leads to mental health risks.

Summary of Findings

From the data analysis in the preceding section of this work, the following are the findings:

- i. The awareness level of Flavour's '*Ukwu Sara Mbara*' and Timaya's '*Bum Bum*' is very high among the undergraduate students of the University of Calabar, Cross River State, and this is highly enhanced by the media.
- ii. The possible reasons for the sexualized presentation of the female in Flavour's '*Ukwu Sara Mbara*' and Timaya's '*Bum Bum*' are appreciation for the nude videos by the younger generation, sensational language/lyrics and objectification of the female gender by the female folk.
- iii. The dominant marketing appeal in Flavour's '*Ukwu Sara Mbara*' and Timaya's '*Bum Bum*' is the sex appeal which has generally disposed women as objects of marketing in those musical videos. This sex appeal is glaringly captured in the dress pattern, language, videos, dance steps and objectification of the woman.

Conclusion

This study examined the image of the woman in selected Flavour's and Timaya's musical videos among undergraduates at the University of Calabar, Cross River State. The study showed that the woman is overused in advertising as marketing programmes. The study in table 3 revealed that Flavour's '*Ukwu Sara Mbara*' and Timaya's '*Bum Bum*' are awash with hyper-sexualized images of the female gender seen in dress pattern (nudity) and sexual advances but highly embraced by the younger generation. This finding is also corroborated by Mbah (2022) and Idorenyin (2019) who observed that the music industry all over the world shows a high rate of hypersexualized portrayal and other negative presentations of the women. The negative portrayal of the female in Flavour's '*Ukwu Sara Mbara*' and Timaya's '*Bum Bum*' is also promoted by the females who allow themselves to be used as video vixens, and this has a strong tendency to weaken the fight against female misrepresentation and objectification in the society.

Recommendations

In the light of the above findings, recommendations for this study are as follow:

- i. Considering the high awareness level of the studied songs, Flavour and Timaya who have garnered many fans should use their songs to advocate good ideals and promote African values as their songs have far reach.

- ii. The media – both the mainstream and the social media should give attention to the promotion of musical videos that promote the sanity of the society and ensure the promotion and preservation of local content so as preserve local culture and values as well as reduce the erosion effect of the infiltration of foreign content.
- iii. The objectification of women and their use as marketing strategies in advertising should be checkmated by the media in order to dowse or attenuate a wrong but sustained view of women in the society, particularly in the contemporary times.

References

- Ajose, K. (2015). 10 shocking Nigerian music videos in recent times. Retrieved from <https://www.vangyardngr.com>. 11/04/2023. 11:18am.
- Ekwenchi, O. C., & Duru, H. (2016). Women in Nigerian music video: what undergrads think. *International Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities Reviews*.6 (3). 22-30. <https://www.ijsshr.com/journal/index/IJSSHR/article/view/250/225>. 1/04/2023. 3:10pm.
- Ekwunife, R. A., Chukwu, C. O., Agha, O.G., Ukeje. I. O and Anih, C.A. (2021). Mass media and politics in Nigeria: The age-long war. In Farazmand (ed). *Global Encyclopedia of Public Administration, Public Policy, and Governance*. Springer Nature. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-31816-5_4344-1.
- Frisby, M., & Aubrey, J. S. (2012). Race and genre in the use of sexual objectification in female artists' music videos. Retrieved from <https://www.tandonline.com/toi/uhjc20>. 11/04/2023. 11:15am.
- Glantz, J. (2013). Women in popular music media: empowered or exploited? *The Spectrum. Scholar Day Journal*. 2 (1). 1-5.
- Oberiri. D. A., & Jigem, L. G. (2019). Portrayal and objectification of women in music videos: A review of existing studies. <https://www.researchgate.net/publications>. 11/04/2023. 05:00pm.
- Idorenyi, S. (2019). The image portrayal of women in Nigerian popular music. Retrieved from <https://projectsolutionz.com.ng>. 10/05/2023. 11:09am.
- Jordan L. (2019). The importance of music videos. <http://radio.rutgers.edu/the-importance-of-music-videos/>. 10/05/2023. 11:09am.
- Mbah, P. (2022). Artiste decries rate of nudity in musical videos. Retrieved from [doi:10.1007/s11199-016-0727-6](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11199-016-0727-6). 11/04/2023. 10:11am.
- Ndolo, I. S. (2011). *Mass Media Systems*. Enugu. Rhyce Kerex.
- Okunna, C.S., & Omenugha, K. A. (2012). *Introduction to Mass Communication*. Enugu. New Generation Books.
- Okunna, C.S. (1993). Global communication and cultural synchronization. In Okunna, Amafili & Okenwa (eds). *Theory and Practice of Mass Communication*. Enugu. Abic Publishers.
- Qamar, A., Pasha, K., & Ali, J. (2021). Examining the females' objectification in music videos from Martha Nussbaum's perspective. Retrieved from <https://www.researchgate.net/publications>. 11/04/2023. 05:05pm
- Sarna, D. (2021). Feminism, gender and pop music. Retrieved from <https://safetyBlogs.com>. 11/04/2023. 07:20pm.
- Serena, D., Mariska., & Sadza, A. (2017). Gender representation on gender-targeted television channels: A comparison of female and male-targeted TV channels in the Netherlands. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11199-016-0727-6>. 11/04/2023. 07:28pm.
- Simon, O. and Besong, E. (2016). Nigerian media and indigenous cultures transformation: The journey so far. *Journal of Mass Communication and Journalism* <https://www.researchgate.net/311159789>. 28/11/2024. 01:12pm.